

IMPLEMENTATION BERTHING AND CAST OFF COMMUNICATION IN SHIP COMMUNICATION AT TANJUNG EMAS HARBOUR, INDONESIA

Ario Hendartono¹

Department Nautical Studies
Politeknik Maritim Negeri Indonesia
Semarang, Indonesia

Abstract:

In the modern era, a ship is equipped with all the modern communication equipment, like VHF telephony, MF radio telephony, HF telephony. Besides that, seafarers need a specific communication for transferring information when berthing and cast off situation. Sea communication is chosen, and needed to be explored in this research: what channel, medium and code as the concept of communication are used in berthing and cast off situation. In conducting of the study, this research used qualitative approach for unfolding the channel, medium and code as the concept of communication. The subject of the study was Semarang pilot and the ocean going ship. In this research used two ships with different length, the first she has length less than 200 metre and the other more 200 metre. The research recorded the communication when the ship entered to the harbour and cast off from the harbour. The result revealed that in berthing MV. Jessica used "command" 22 times, in cast off only 5 times, MV. Jo Brevick used 20 times command in berthing and in cass off only 5 times too. It points out that the command in berthing gave more than cast off situation.

Keywords: berthing, cast off, channel, medium, code

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

When we sail on board ship, we need communication because communication will transfer information from you to the coast station or another ship. Communication can provide information so the ship can survive from the disaster. In the ancient ships, communication was not as good as like now, for example RMS Titanic. If at that time communication was good, the accident on the RMS Titanic can be avoided. When the RMS Titanic was sending news of the danger, a ship passing nearby not knowing. The

¹ Correspondence: email ariohend@polimarin.ac.id

three basic concepts in communication, which is channel, code and medium (Fiske, John 1994:17). Channel is the physical means by which the signal is transmitted may be from a ship, car, aircraft or otherwise. The main channels are radio waves, light waves, telephone cable, sound waves, the nervous system and the like. Radio waves propagate from one place to another through the air like in radio stations, radio walkies that convert sound into radio waves and so received by the recipient in the change again into sound. While the medium is the carrier of something, the medium provides the transmission or storage of information data so that can be said medium in communication is a tool or means used to convey messages from communicators to the audience. The dominant medium in communicating is the human senses like the ears and the eyes. Whereas the code in the communication is a rule for converting an information into another form or representation, which does not have to be in the same form. In communication and information processing, encoding is the process of converting information from a source (object) into data, which is then transmitted to the receiver or observer as in data processing systems. Encoding in communication means the act of giving meaning or symbol.

1.2 Problem Identification

Based on the back ground description can be identified problems as follows:

1. The lack of detailed description of the use of maritime communications that pour in the channel as part of the concept of communication especially in the implementation berthing and cast off communication at Tanjung Emas harbour.
2. The lack of detailed description of the use of maritime communications that pour in the medium as part of the concept of communication especially in the implementation berthing and cast off communication at Tanjung Emas harbour.
3. The lack of detailed description of the use of maritime communications that pour in the code as part of the concept of communication especially in the implementation berthing and cast off communication at Tanjung Emas harbour.

1.3 Restricting the Problem

In this writing is restricted the time of communication when implementation communication in berthing and cast off at Tanjung Emas harbour.

1.4 Problem Statements

Based on the description above can be formulated he problems of the research as follows:

1. What channels are used in implementation communication in berthing and cast off at Tanjung Emas harbour?
2. What media are used in implementation communication in berthing and cast off at Tanjung Emas harbour?
3. What codes are used in implementation communication in berthing and cast off at Tanjung Emas harbour?

1.5 The Purpose of the Study

1. Identifying the channels are used in implementation in berthing and cast off at Tanjung Emas harbour.
2. Identifying the media are used in implementation in berthing and cast off at Tanjung Emas harbour.
3. Identifying the codes are used in implementation in berthing and cast off at Tanjung Emas harbour

1.6 The Significance of the Study

It is hoped that the findings of this study will give great advantages for the following groups of people:

1. This research will give a great benefit to the lecturer of maritime English who is concerned with the case study at Tanjung Emas harbour: Implementation Berthing and Cast off communication at Tanjung Emas harbour.
2. This research will also give more advantages to the students from maritime field especially to know about channels, medium and code in berthing and cast off communication.
3. The community of seafares to know more about channels, medium and code in berthing and cast off communication.

2. Review of Related Literature

According to Fiske (1994:17), the three concepts of communication are: channel, medium and code.

A. Channel

Channel is one of the simplest concepts of communication. It is simply the physical means by which the signal is transmitted, therefore in this research the focus is on the vessel will be berthed and cast off at Tanjung Emas harbour.

B. Medium

The medium is basically the physical or technical means of converting the messages into signals capable of being transmitted along the channel. The human voice is a medium; the technology of broadcasting is what constitutes the media of television and radio. The technological or physical properties of a medium are determined by the nature of the channel or channels available for its use. These properties of the medium then determine the range of codes which it can transmit.

The researcher can divide media into three main categories.

- a) The presentational media: They use the natural languages of spoken words, expression, gestures, and so on. They require the presence of the communicator, for he or she is the medium, they are restricted to the here and now, and produce acts of communication.
- b) The representational media: paintings, writing and gardening, etc.
- c) The mechanical media: radio, television, telephone etc.

C. Code

A code is about a system of meaning common to the members of culture or subculture. It consists both of signs (i.e. physical signals that stand for something other than themselves) and of rules or conventions that determine how and in what contexts these signs are used and how they can be combined to form more complex messages.

3. Research Design

In this research will be more in detail about the basic concept of communication in this case is channel, medium and code when implementation berthing and cast off communication in ship communication at Tanjung Emas harbour.

3.1 Research Approach

In conducting of this study, the research used a qualitative approach. In this research would be described the channel, the medium and the code.

3.2 Source of the Data

This research was done at Tanjung Emas harbour when the vessel would be berthed and cast off. There were two vessels would be researched, the first was the vessel has length over all (LOA) less than 200 metres and another ship has LOA more than 200 metres. This data is taken using a pilot boat from Semarang pilot the vessel.

3.3 Research Setting

This research was conducted from 2007 to 2008 using a pilot boat from Semarang pilot station with two pilots, sea pilot and harbour pilot to the fairway at outer breakwater and to the berthing position then from cast off position. All conversation and information are recorded using recorder.

3.4 Procedure of Collecting Data

The entire implementation of the research by permission of the manager of pelabuhan Semarang III (Pelindo III).

3.5 Procedures of Data Analysis

In the implementation was divided into several steps:

- a) The conversation was recorded by using the recorder.
- b) The use of flag attributes for communication was also noted.
- c) Identifying all data into channel, medium and code.

4. Findings

A. The Ship's particular MSC Jessica

Vessel type : Container ship

Flag	: Panama
Gross tonnage	: 18140 tons
Deadweight	: 23991 tons
Length	: 202 m
Breadth	: 29 m
Draft	: 10 m

The flags that are on the vessel:

- Panama flag
- Indonesian flag
- Company flag
- Golf flag
- Bravo flag
- Hotel flag

Cargo	: Containers
Communication aids	: VHF
	: HT (Handie Talkie)
	: Horn

Piloting data

Date of piloting	: 13 December 2007
Duration of piloting	: 10.00 am - 01.40 pm

Weather Condition

Sea condition	: Slight to moderate (3 to 4 in Beaufort scale)
Sky condition	: Blue cloudy

Name of tug boats

Tug number one	: TB. Kasih ibu
Tug number two	: TB. Abrar Utama
Tug number three	: TB. Anoman III

Pilot boat approached MV. Jessica about from 3.5 NM (nautical miles) from break water. A pilot ladder was ready on the starboard bow for pilot boarding. After 30 minutes of sailing from pilot station , the pilot boarded and gave advice to the master for berthing.

The channel on the concept of communication used:

Channel 12	: It is used for piloting between Semarang pilot and MV. Jessica.
Channel 14	: It is used sea pilot on the vessel and tug boat.
Channel 16	: It is used for emergency
Horn	: It is sound signal for alert.

The main channel was radio waves (CH 12, 14 and 16) and sound wave during piloting was horn.

The Medium on the concept of communication used:

The presentational media:

- a) The voice sometimes used SMCP (Standard Marine Communication and Phrases) from the pilot to the tug boat, its aims to give orders to the tugboat to keep MV. Jessica in the right position.
 - b) The body from the pilot, master and the crews gave the signal during piloting through some signal gestures
 - c) The face from the pilot, maseter and the crews showed from the expressions with the serious face during piloting.
- The representational media: The master used a pilot book for piloting.
 - The mechanical media: VHF radio, HT (Handie Talkie) and signal Horn.

The codes on the concept of communication used:

During piloting in berthing, I got some codes:

- a) The national flag was put on the stern of ship.
- b) The Golf flag was put on the top mast in port side (left side) which is meaning *"I require a pilot"*
- c) The Hotel flag was put on the top mast in port side which is meaning *"I have a pilot"* when the hotel flag was raised then the Golf flag is lowered because the pilot was already on the vessel.
- d) The Bravo flag was put on the top mast in port side which is meaning *"I am taking in carrying dangerous cargo"*.
- e) Company flag was put on the top mast in port side.
- f) Indonesian flag was put on the top mast in starboard side (right side).

Cast off Communication

Piloting data

Date of piloting : 15 December 2007
Duration of piloting : 08.00 am - 10.25 am

Weather Condition

Sea condition : Slight sea (3 in Beauford scale)
Sky condition : Blue sky

Name of tug boats

Tug number one : TB. Kasih ibu
Tug number two : TB. Abrar Utama
Tug number three : TB. Anoman III

Basically the concept of cast off communication for channel, medium and code is the same as berthing only time of use. When cast off the Bravo flag was not hoisted in because of all the dangerous cargoes or goods had been discharged.

The Channel on the concept of communication used:

Channel 12 : It is used for piloting between Semarang pilot and MV. Jessica.

Channel 14 : It is used sea pilot on the vessel and tug boat.

Channel 16 : It is used for emergency

Horn : It is sound signal for alert.

The main channel was radio waves (CH 12, 14 and 16) and sound wave during piloting was horn.

The Medium on the concept of communication used:

The presentational media:

- a) The voice sometimes used SMCP (Standard Marine Communication and Phrases) from the pilot to the tug boat, its aims to give orders to the tugboat to keep MV. Jessica in the right position.
 - b) The body from the pilot, master and the crews gave the signal during piloting through some signal gestures
 - c) The face from the pilot, maseter and the crews showed from the expressions with the serious face during piloting.
- The representational media: The master used a pilot book for piloting.
 - The mechanical media: VHF radio, HT (Handie Talkie) and signal Horn.

The codes on the concept of communication used:

During piloting in berthing, I got some codes:

- a) The national flag was put on the stern of ship.
- b) The Golf flag was put on the top mast in port side (left side) which has meaning *"I require a pilot"*.
- c) The Hotel flag was put on the top mast in port side which has meaning *"I have a pilot"* when the hotel flag was raised then the Golf flag is lowered because the pilot was already on the vessel.
- d) Company flag was put on the top mast in port side.
- e) Indonesian flag was put on the top mast in starboard side (right side).

B. For the second ship Motor Tanker Jo Brevick (MT. Jo Brevict)

Vessel type	: oil/ chemical Tanker
Flag	: Norway International Register
Gross tonnage	: 19,688 tons
Summer DWT	: 33,000 tons
LOA	: 182 m
IMO	: 8416322

The flags that are on the vessel:

- Norway flag
- Indonesian flag
- Company flag

- Golf flag
- Bravo flag
- Hotel flag

Cargo : Liquid cargo (Palm Oil)
Communication aids : VHF
: HT (Handie Talkie)
: Horn

Piloting data

Date of piloting : 17 December 2007
Duration of piloting : 11:30 to 13:55

Weather Condition

Sea condition : Rough sea (5 in Beauford scale)
Sky condition : Blue cloudy

Name of tug boats

Tug number one : TB. Kasih ibu
Tug number two : TB. Anoman III

Basically a vessel with a length of more than 200 m with a vessel of less than 200 m for channel, medium and code are the same as berthing only time of use. The difference in berthing and cast off at motor tanker Jo Brevick, the bravo flag was hoisted.

References

1. Blakey, T. N. English for Maritime Studies. London: Prentice Hall International, (1987)
2. Clarke, J. P. Admiralty Charts and Publications. Somerset: The United Kingdom Hydrographic Office, (1999)
3. Clarke, J. P. Admiralty Sailing Direction "Indonesian Pilot Volume II. Somerset: The United Kingdom Hydrographic Office, (1999)
4. Embankment, Albert. Standard Marine Communication Phrases. London, (1997)
5. Fiske, John. Introduction To Communication Studies: London: Guernsey, (1994)
6. Hughes, Cyril. Dictionary of Marine Technology. London: Headway, (1997)
7. Kluijven, Van, P, C., The International Maritime Language Programmed. Rotterdam: ALK & Heijnen, (2002)
8. Maxwell, A. J. Qualitative Research Design. An Interactive Approach. London: SAGE, (1996)
9. Rahayu, Sri Tutie. "Power Hegemony: Maritime Organizational Transformation Dialectics On Politeknik Maritim Negeri, Indonesia" European Journal of Education Studies [Online], (20 August 2017)
10. Santoso, Gunawan Budi. "The Influence of Boarding Education Pattern on The Strengthening of Technology Based Characters of Polimarin Students" European Journal of Education Studies [Online], (20 August 2017)

11. Swift, F. N. I., 2004. Bridge Team Management. London: The Nautical Institute, (2004)

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).